

DUAL-SURFACE ENGINEERING OF CARBON FIBERS BY GRAFTING CARBON NANOTUBES AND CHEMICAL FUNCTIONALIZATION

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Keywords: Carbon fiber; Carbon nanotubes; Interface/interphase; Chemical vapor deposition (CVD); Surface treatments; Pultrusion; Micro-mechanics

ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites, performance remains constrained by fiber–matrix adhesion due to the chemically inert and smooth surfaces of the untreated fibers (CFs). Chemical compatibility is usually improved by electro-oxidation followed by sizing to improve the mechanical properties, particularly in epoxy-matrix composites. Grafting carbon nanotubes (CNTs) onto CFs by chemical vapour deposition (CVD) improves mechanical interlocking but generates a chemically inert surface. This study shows that combining CNT grafting with a simple chemical treatment (sizing or epoxidation) activates the surface and maximises interfacial strength between epoxy matrix and modified fibers. Surface analysis confirmed increased oxygen content and polarity from these treatments. Single-fiber pull-out tests demonstrated that sized CNT-g-CF in an epoxy matrix achieved up to 60% higher interfacial shear strength than both unsized CFs and as-produced (unsized) CNT-g-CF. Flexural testing of unidirectional fiber reinforced epoxy composite rods (40% V_f) showed a 30% increase in flexural strength compared to unsized CFs and an 8% gain over as-produced (unsized) CNT-

g-CFs. These results highlight that chemical modification is essential to fully exploit the potential of CNT-enhanced interfaces in epoxy-based matrices.

1 INTRODUCTION

In carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites, the fiber–matrix interface governs load transfer and stress distribution, directly influencing strength and toughness. However, untreated carbon fibers (CFs) have chemically inert surfaces, low surface energy, and minimal roughness, which limit bonding with polymer matrices such as epoxy-based matrices and lead to poor load transfer and reduced mechanical performance [1,2]. Conventional methods such as chemical modification (oxidation or sizing) or nanoscale roughening (grafting carbon nanotubes (CNTs), nanorods, or whiskers) can improve fiber–matrix adhesion but each has drawbacks. Strong oxidative treatments, for example, enhance surface reactivity but can degrade CF tensile strength, creating a trade-off between reactivity and structural integrity [3]. Grafting CNTs improves interfacial properties through mechanical interlocking and a larger interphase interaction volume [4], yet the high temperatures used in chemical vapour deposition (CVD) can damage the CF structure. Recent developments have enabled the continuous production of uniformly CNT-grafted CF tows, avoiding any fiber damage. However, to maximise the benefits of CNT-grafted-CFs (CNT-g-CF), chemical compatibility with the epoxy matrix must also be considered, since the as grown CNTs are chemically inert and the CVD growth conditions strip the oxide groups from the CF surface. After grafting, epoxy-based CNT-g-CF composites have a complex hierarchical structure, consisting of three coupled interfaces, as illustrated in Figure 1: CNT/CF, CNT/matrix, and CF/matrix, compared to the traditional single planar CF/matrix interface.

To identify which interface limits efficient stress transfer, each must be considered. Reported interfacial shear strength (IFSS) values in the literature vary widely (30–270 MPa) for CNT-epoxy interfaces [5], depending on factors such as CNT diameter, length, and surface defects, which enhance mechanical interlocking, together with experimental measurement difficulties. The CNT/CF junctions, formed during CVD growth, can achieve bond strengths approaching 200 MPa which far exceeds the van der Waals limit [6]. In contrast, the CF/epoxy interface is often the weakest region in unsized carbon fiber reinforced systems, with IFSS typically ranging from 30–60 MPa due to the chemically inert CF surface [2]. Note if the whole system is considered, CNT-g-CF/epoxy interfaces values also vary widely and can be affected by matrix choice (between different epoxies) and the method used to determine IFSS (~30–166 MPa) [7]. For this reason, it is often good practice to evaluate these modified fibers with an appropriate baseline and consider relative improvements.

As significant portion of the CNT-g-CF surface includes this CF/epoxy interface, any improvements to the CF/epoxy interphase region is likely to produce overall improvements in IFSS for CNT-g-CF/epoxy systems. The effect of post-treatment on any as-produced CNT-g-CFs has not been reported in relation to the IFSS in an epoxy matrix. Therefore, combining CNT grafting (mechanical) with chemical post-treatments could further improve these interfacial characteristics. An optimal fiber–matrix interface combines chemical bonding and mechanical interlocking to fully exploit the primary reinforcing fiber (CF in this instance) strength. This study demonstrates that integrating CNT-g-CFs with sizing or epoxidation achieves dual-surface engineering, demonstrating a synergistic improvement in CFRP interfacial properties.

Figure 1: Schematic of CNT-reinforced interphase and its constituent interfaces.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Unsize as-received carbon fibers (AS4-12K-7D, HS-CP-5000 grade, Hexcel) and as-produced CNT-g-CFs (prepared using a continuous CVD process described elsewhere [8]) were used. For the sizing treatment, a solvent-based epoxy sizing was prepared by dissolving 1.25 wt.% PRIME 27 epoxy resin (Gurit) in acetone ($\geq 99.5\%$, Sigma-Aldrich); fibers were held under tension and dipped for ~ 2 min and then dried overnight at room temperature. Epoxidation involved immersing fibers in a 1 wt.% meta-chloroperoxybenzoic acid ($\geq 77\%$, Sigma-Aldrich) solution in dichloromethane ($\geq 99.5\%$) at room temperature for 3 h, rinsing in pure dichloromethane for 1 h, and drying at 80°C for 30 min. Composite rods were fabricated by continuous fiber pultrusion. The fibers were tensioned on a spool, pulled through a bath of bisphenol A-based PRIME 27 epoxy resin with extra slow PRIME 27 hardener (Gurit), and guided through a 1.2 mm nozzle to control fiber volume fraction. Tension was applied during curing to maintain rod shape. Composites were cured at room temperature for 24 h, cut to length, and post-cured at 50°C for 16 h.

Fiber morphology was examined using a Zeiss Sigma 300 field emission scanning electron microscope (SEM) operated at 5 kV with an in-lens detector; samples were mounted on aluminium stubs with conductive silver paint. Fiber surface chemistry was analysed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy using a Thermo Fisher K-Alpha+ system with a monochromated Al $K\alpha$ source, keeping the chamber pressure below 5×10^{-7} mbar; fibers were cut to 10 mm, mounted on Cu-based holders with carbon double-sided tape and metallic clips. Interfacial shear strength (IFSS) was determined by single-fiber pull-out test. Single filaments were embedded in epoxy droplet, with embedded lengths controlled below $80\ \mu\text{m}$ to avoid fiber breakage, then pre-cured at 150°C for 10 min, followed by room temperature curing for 24 h and post-curing at 50°C for 16 h (following manufacturers recommendations). Single-fiber pull-out tests were performed using a KISTLER 9207 piezoelectric force sensor and a PICA P-216.9S actuator ($180\ \mu\text{m}$ travel, 50 N capacity); fibers were aligned and glued to the actuator needle with Born2Bond cyanoacrylate, UV-cured for 20 s, and pulled at $250\ \text{nm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. Flexural strength of composite rods was measured by three-point bending test using a Linkam MFS modular force stage with a 200 N load cell; samples (60 mm long) were tested on a 30 mm support span at $1\ \text{mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ rate until failure.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Surface morphology and chemistry

Surface morphology is crucial for the fiber-matrix interphase, contributing through mechanical interlocking. SEM analysis (Figure 2) shows that sizing introduced noticeable surface changes. Both CFs and CNT-g-CFs were uniformly coated with resin, indicating effective wetting. In sized CNT-g-CFs, the CNT network was embedded in the resin. To quantify these effects, average roughness (R_a) was measured from SEM images as semi-quantitative method using Equation 1 through ImageJ software

(version 1.54m). The examined profiles were taken from regions less than 1 μm in length and 15% in diameter to minimize curvature effects, keeping sampling consistent to ensure comparability. Histogram stretching was also applied to enhance contrast. The CNT-g-CFs showed higher roughness ($R_a = 21.4$) due to the grafted nanotube network (Table 1). Sizing reduced surface roughness in both fibers. For CFs, the change was minimal, likely from resin filling surface features. In contrast, CNT-g-CFs showed a more noticeable decrease in R_a , aligning with the collapse and embedding of the CNT network in the sizing layer. This smoothing could impact resin infiltration, fiber packing, and interfacial mechanics in composite fabrication.

$$Ra = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |y_i - \bar{y}| \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: SEM micrographs of baseline carbon fibers and after sizing surface treatment in comparison to CNT-g-CF.

Table 1: X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy for surface composition of carbon fiber-based samples.

Element (at. %)	As-received unsize CF	Epoxidized CF	Lab-sized CF	As-produced CNT-g-CF	Epoxidized CNT-g-CF	Lab-sized CNT-g-CF
Oxygen	5.9	23.4	37.8	3.6	17.2	35.4
Carbon	94.1	76.6	62.2	96.4	82.8	64.6

3.2 Interfacial performance

The apparent IFSS (Figure 3) was calculated based on Equation 2 where one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test showed no significant IFSS differences between as-produced CNT-g-CFs and unsize CFs, indicating CNT grafting process did not necessarily enhance interfacial performance in the Prime 27 epoxy. Likely, the loss of reactivity of the previously oxidised CF, led to a weak CF/matrix interface and premature debonding, counteracting any benefit of the mechanical interlocking effect. Lab-sized CFs increased IFSS by 35%, demonstrating the sizing benefits for compatibility with thermosetting matrices. While epoxidation did not show great benefit with unsize CF, the epoxidized CNT-grafted-

CFs improved IFSS by 28% over as-produced (unsized) CNT-g-CF, with oxidative treatment facilitating matrix interaction. This exploitation of surface modification using CNT-g-CFs was even stronger with sizing, achieving over 60% IFSS increase (lab-sized CNT-g-CF). In low-reactivity epoxies like Prime 27, the resin bonds weakly to CF, so CNT functionalisation adds active sites that improve interfacial adhesion and load transfer. Without functionalization, CNTs mainly act as topographical elements, underlining the synergy between mechanical interlocking by CNTs and chemical compatibility from sizing.

$$IFSS = \frac{F_d}{\pi dl_{emb}} \quad (2)$$

3.3 Flexural properties

To evaluate composite flexural performance, three-point bending tests were performed on pultruded rods (40% V_f , void content below 3%), which subjects specimens to combined tensile, compressive, and shear stresses. This configuration captures how interfacial enhancements translate to macroscopic bending behavior, which involves different failure mechanisms than local fiber pull-out. The flexural strength is calculated using Equation 3 and results were normalized to the nominal composite diameter (Figure 3). Lab-sized CNT-g-CF reinforced composites exhibited a 30% increase in flexural strength compared to unsized CF reinforced composites, demonstrating that combining CNT grafting with sizing improves fiber–matrix bonding and multiscale stress transfer. Sizing also enhanced flexural strength in CF reinforced composites, although the effect was more pronounced with CNT grafting due to the additional mechanical interlocking and stiffening of matrix. In contrast, epoxidation improved interfacial shear strength but did not significantly increase flexural strength under these conditions, highlighting that strong fiber–matrix adhesion alone is insufficient without optimized matrix wettability and improved interfacial properties.

$$\sigma_f = \frac{FL}{\pi R^3} \quad (3)$$

Figure 3: For corresponding modified carbon fibers interfacial shear strength was determined through single-fiber pullout test in an epoxy matrix, and flexural strength via 3-point bending test (40% V_f unidirectional epoxy composite rods).

4 CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrates that carbon nanotube grafting alone does not fully overcome the limitations of untreated carbon fibers due to their inert surfaces in composites. Combining carbon nanotube-grafted-carbon fibers with targeted chemical treatments, such as sizing, creates a dual-surface engineered interface that improves the overall fiber–matrix adhesion and enables more efficient stress transfer. This synergy provided up to 60% higher interfacial shear strength and ~30% greater flexural strength compared to unsized carbon fibers. These results highlight the importance of integrating chemical compatibility and mechanical interlocking to maximize the performance of hierarchical interfaces in carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors kindly acknowledge the funding for this research provided by UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) programme Grant EP/T011653/1, Next Generation Fiber-Reinforced Composites (NextCOMP): a Full Scale Redesign for Compression a collaboration between Imperial College London and the University of Bristol. For the purpose of open access, the authors has applied a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license to any author accepted manuscript version arising.

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